

INCREASING THE TECHNOLOGICAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS

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Annotation. This article aims to increase the technological component of students with special needs.

Key words: inclusive education, education, memory, speech, complex construction, cognitive development.

Currently, the changes implemented in the education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan, including the development of inclusive education, guarantee equal rights in education for students with disabilities in special boarding schools. This is relevant today because it is important not to give the child as much knowledge as possible, but to ensure his general cultural, personal and cognitive development, to arm him with such an important skill. Currently, in modern practice, there is certain positive experience of introducing inclusion into the process of teaching technology in special boarding schools. Knowing the technological component helps children with disabilities to learn a trade, to be independent and not have difficulties in communicating with their peers.

With the help of this, the main task of inclusive education - socialization of children with disabilities - is being implemented. This means that they will have the opportunity to find their place in life, but only at their level of development. Thus, the goal of teaching technology for children with disabilities is to develop. It is necessary to develop the memory, speech, attention, thinking and outlook of technological students. Such students may not be able to fully master complex constructions and agreements, because they have a low level of mental development. Sometimes you can include these constructions, but only for familiarity. In the planning of lessons in the integrated classroom, in addition to traditional lessons: education, upbringing and development, as well as the goal of correction.

Psychologists say that if you carefully study and educate children with mental retardation, they are able to adapt and become a harmonious part of modern society. At the same time, organizing children with disabilities in specialized schools and boarding schools for disabled persons fully meets the requirements of the present time.

The main categories of children with disabilities include:

1. Children with impaired hearing (deaf, hard of hearing, late deafness);
2. Children with visual impairment (blind, low vision);
3. Children with speech disorders (logopaths);
4. Children with impaired locomotor function;
5. Mentally retarded children;
6. Children with impaired behavior and communication;
7. Children with complex disorders of psychophysical development, so-called complex defects (blind, deaf or mentally retarded children).

In order for disabled children to find their place in life, they must learn a certain profession. Life in the modern world is impossible without the Internet (communication, work), and for full-fledged activity in this field, you need to know computer technologies. The main and leading goal of teaching technology in specialized schools and boarding schools is the communicative goal that determines the entire educational process. Currently, the experience of teaching children with disabilities on an equal basis with students with normal development is being actively formed. This type of educational practice is based on the idea of accepting the individuality of each student, so the process should be organized in such a way as to meet the needs of a disabled child.

Therefore, the purpose of this work is to study the modern technologies of teaching technology in order to involve children with physical disabilities in the educational process and improve their results. Inclusive education is based on special didactic principles that must be followed in the planning and organization of lessons. It is impossible to correct all mental processes during one lesson.

The topic itself determines which analyzers will participate more in the lesson. The corrective-developing task should be very clear. In general, none of the scholars require a detailed, precise formulation of the correction task, because it is not easy, but a clear direction of correction is still a prerequisite for a good lesson. It should be done in this way, since it is permissible to draw up a general plan for the class, which includes blocks of tasks for each child who needs an individual approach and additional attention according to developmental characteristics.

Forms may be different; the main thing is to reflect the activity trajectory of an individual child in the class of "peaceful" children during the lesson. In classes for students with disabilities, the content of technology is mainly taught in two different ways. The first includes theoretical and the second practical information, in which the teacher prepares and demonstrates the item prepared in practical training in order to form and develop knowledge and skills related to mastering practical activities.

The organization of technology classes for children with disabilities based on educational principles serves to form and develop the reproductive activity of

students. The majority of students with disabilities may have an insufficient level of cognitive activity, lack of motivation for educational activities, reduced efficiency and independence.

Therefore, the search for and use of active forms, methods and methods of teaching is one of the necessary means of increasing the effectiveness of the process of correction and development.

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